

Supproting Table S1:

Consensus protein interactors of GFP-*Nt*ARPC2, identified in both repetitions of proteomic analysis.

Protein ID (Uniprot)	FASTA headers	PTS	intensity 1 (max. 26.3574)	intensity 2 (max. 26.1078)
A0A1S4DR85 A0A1S3ZA87	Actin-related protein 2/3 complex subunit OS Actin-related protein 2/3 complex subunit OS		21.9136	23.7485
G0WLG3	Arp2/3 complex 34 kDa subunit OS		26.3574	26.1078
A0A1S3Z3H1 A0A1S3WXP2	Actin-related protein 2/3 complex subunit 3 OS Actin-related protein 2/3 complex subunit 3 OS		21.5897	21.9216
A0A1S4BTZ8	Actin-related protein 2/3 complex subunit 4 OS		21.176	24.4566
A0A1S3ZCR5	Actin-related protein 2/3 complex subunit 5 OS		21.4188	24.1816
A0A1S4DI60	actin-related protein 3 OS		21.5047	23.0667
A0A1S4A550 A0A1S4A514 A0A1S4A4Y5 A0A1S4A581	actin-related protein 3 isoform X4 OS actin-related protein 3 isoform X3 OS actin-related protein 3 isoform X2 OS actin-related protein 3 isoform X1 OS		19.7576	21.8903
A0A1S4A6H4	peroxisomal fatty acid beta-oxidation multifunctional protein AIM1-like OS	PTS1	22.3573	22.0314
A0A1S4DNE8	peroxisomal fatty acid beta-oxidation multifunctional protein AIM1-like OS	PTS1	20.9527	20.1321
A0A1S3XY53	peroxisomal fatty acid beta-oxidation multifunctional protein AIM1-like OS	PTS1	19.5933	22.0314
A0A1S4D439	LOW-QUALITY PROTEIN: glyoxysomal fatty acid beta-oxidation multifunctional protein MFP-a-like OS	PTS1	20.2187	19.6894
A0A1S4D6S9 A0A1S4D762 A0A1S4D720 A0A1S4A2D2	4-coumarate--CoA ligase-like 6 isoform X3 OS 4-coumarate--CoA ligase-like 6 isoform X2 OS 4-coumarate--CoA ligase-like 6 isoform X1 OS 4-coumarate--CoA ligase-like 6 OS	PTS1	21.3696	19.7423
A0A1S4AJS0	4-coumarate--CoA ligase-like 7 OS	PTS1	24.8577	22.5521
A0A1S4DHZ4 A0A1S4DQN6	probable quinone oxidoreductase OS probable quinone oxidoreductase OS	PTS1	24.2513	21.5504
A0A1S3Y9E9 A0A1S4D3Y8 A0A1S4ASM7 A0A1S3YQG6	Aspartate aminotransferase OS Aspartate aminotransferase OS Aspartate aminotransferase OS Aspartate aminotransferase OS	PTS2	23.703	20.0947
A0A1S3Z7C4 A0A1S3Z7V8	delta(3,5)-Delta(2,4)-dienoyl-CoA isomerase, peroxisomal isoform X1 OS delta(3,5)-Delta(2,4)-dienoyl-CoA isomerase, peroxisomal isoform X2 OS	PTS1	23.4051	21.0945
A0A1S3Y1Q5 A0A1S3YTH0	acyl-coenzyme A thioesterase 13-like OS acyl-coenzyme A thioesterase 13-like OS	PTS1	21.8947	18.5317
A0A1S3YP09	glyoxysomal processing protease, glyoxysomal-like OS	PTS1	24.5543	21.6784
A0A1S4BMM1 A0A1S3XIF9	gamma-glutamyl peptidase 5-like OS gamma-glutamyl peptidase 5-like OS		22.0176	19.499